

Distributed energy prosumer communities and the application of emerging technologies: A systematic literature review

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Energy internet
Energy prosumer communities
Distributed energy sharing and trading
Artificial intelligence
Internet of things
Distributed ledger technologies

ABSTRACT

Energy prosumer communities offer a mechanism where prosumers can share, and trade locally produced renewable generation directly with consumers within the same energy community. Accordingly, there is need for a decentralized approaches that enables prosumers to locally balance generation and consumption. The deployment of emerging technologies such as Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT), Internet of Things (IoT), and Artificial Intelligence (AI) can accelerate the integration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and advance the development of energy internet. Therefore, this article develops an energy system architecture that shows how DLT, IoT, and AI can be deployed to support the design and actualization of energy internet in Distributed Prosumer Energy Communities (DPEC). The system architecture support energy sharing and trading from energy prosumers to consumer. Findings from this study presents how DLT based smart contracts can be employed to securely manage energy transactions within the energy internet. The system architecture provides energy consumers and prosumers with a decentralized approach for sharing and trading local energy generation without requiring any central intermediary. More importantly, this study presents a use case on the applicability of DLT and AI to support micro grid operations in DPEC.

1. Introduction

Due to the current energy crisis and environmental pressure, communities are moving towards consumption of cleaner electrical energy as part of their strategy to reduce greenhouse gas emission. Thus, several international bodies have been challenged to reduce emissions [53]. For example, the European commission has initiated different legislation to lessen emissions by at least 40 percent by 2030, as part of the European union's (EU) 2030 climate & energy framework [53]. In the EU, the role of energy prosumers as part of the energy internet is important as they can contribute to the development of sustainable power systems, economically efficient, with minimal losses and high degrees of quality and security of energy supply [54]. The decentralization of the energy internet has substantial benefits, mainly facilitating RES to be integrated with local energy resources towards increasing the reliability of the energy internet with a view to accelerate distributed energy prosumer communities [44]. Also, as energy prosumers are gradually being involved in the energy system, new mechanisms and models are being needed to be utilized to operate the power grid in order to decrease energy waste. There is projection that there will emerge new demands

from energy consumers [23]. For example, energy consumers may want to be sure what energy they are consuming and may also prefer to consume green energy.

Also, the large-scale implementation of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) by energy prosumers will bring about new challenges for management of smart grid requiring active participation of energy prosumers, the deployment of decentralized solutions and non-grid owned energy assets. As such local energy flexibility markets can support in achieving local energy balance, monitoring energy flows, motivate behavioral changes in prosumers' energy supply and demand, and optimization of clean electricity flows [4]. The Energy Internet (EI) uses Internet and emerging technologies for harmonized control of RES, energy storage, and loads distribution for compatibility with legacy energy systems towards developing a completely new architecture for future energy system to meet the diverse energy needs of different actors. This is achieved via the sharing of RES, lowering the consumption of fossil generated energy to solve the current energy crisis and environmental pollution faced in the society [57]. The digitalization of the smart grid relies on new actors, business models, and innovative technologies. Thus, innovative technologies are needed to be deployed to help

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sfr.2025.100794>

Received 27 June 2024; Received in revised form 29 May 2025; Accepted 6 June 2025

Available online 6 June 2025

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decentralized and accelerate distributed energy prosumer communities, while simultaneously supporting these communities transitioning to a more decarbonized and sustainable energy system [3].

Evidence from the literature suggested that the deployment of emerging technologies to support the energy internet in generation clean energy both on and off the grid is anticipated to continue in prosumer energy communities (<https://www.iea.org/reports/tracking-clean-energy-progress-2023>). The deployment of emerging technologies such as Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) based Machine Learning (ML) can rapidly enhance access to clean energy thereby directly contributing to low-carbon and sustainable energy systems [3]. DLT such as blockchain offers several potentials for the energy sector by creating opportunities for energy systems in distributed energy prosumer communities, such as energy production, green certificate registries, peer-to-peer (P2P) energy markets, etc. Using DLT microgrids gateways can collect and process data interoperable from different devices ([15]; Jnr et al., 2023). DLT employs a decentralized architecture without needing any intermediaries and can promote energy democratization processes and distributed energy production. DLT can be implemented to provide incentivization schemes where participants within the distributed prosumer energy community are given financial reward for sharing electrical energy [26].

Furthermore, AI based ML can help to manage the transmission of electricity from energy producers to consumers with the aid of digital systems for control automation, optimization of the distribution systems, and continuous monitoring of the overall state of the energy grid to lessen the cost and improve the reliability [1]. ML can be employed for efficient inverter control of Photovoltaic (PV) systems to maximize the possibility to track electricity produced [51]. The prediction offered by ML based analytics aims to minimize uncertainty thereby providing benchmarks to control the real performance of electricity networks [1]. Thus, this article aims to investigate the following research questions.

- How can DLT enable the distributed storage of electrical energy related data and also enable energy transactions in a secured and tamper proof manner.
- How can AI and Internet of Things (IoT) support the development of a distributed energy prosumer communities?
- How can DLT, smart contracts, and AI enable a decentralized peer-to-peer local energy sharing and trading in distributed energy prosumer communities?

Therefore, the main contribution of this article is to develop an energy system architecture that shows how energy internet with DLT and AI can be deployed to support the design and actualization of prosumer energy communities. The energy system architecture offers a citizen centric approach for decentralized energy market design and modelling of a local energy market for residential buildings. Also, this study is motivated to explore the integration of DLT and AI are employed to achieve a scalable prosumer-based service designed specifically to manage and control user nodes in microgrids applications to operate intelligently. This study aims to fill in this gap by exploring the rapidly evolving transition electrical energy studies regarding the conceptualization and the role of energy prosumers in the development of citizen centric approaches and in the unfolding radical community change in DEPC. Therefore, this study aims to support energy exchanges among citizens in distributed energy prosumer communities, mainly in residential buildings to decrease CO₂ emissions in community level using DLT, IoT, and AI technologies to decentralize energy consumption, accelerate energy sharing, towards ensuring a societal transition toward a cleaner energy use. Findings from this article will provide a shift to the transition towards more distributed and integrated energy systems, where the sharing and trading of RES between energy consumers and prosumers is enabled by IoT and AI. The remainder of the paper is as follows: Section 2 presents the theoretical overview and Section 3 describes the method and materials used in this research. Section 4 mainly

present the main findings and Section 5 is the discussion and implications. Lastly, Section 6 is the conclusion of the study.

2. Theoretical overview

Over the last years a few studies have highlighted the challenges faced in energy communities by employing emerging technologies for power balancing, operation, etc. in RES such as photo-voltaic systems, wind turbines, hydropower, etc. [19]. This section reviews prior studies that employed emerging technologies for distributed energy sharing and/or trading in energy communities. Among these studies Hasan et al. [24] researched on the deployment of blockchain to support big data, smart grid, and energy trading. The study mainly presented a review of how the implementations of blockchain can improve the cyber security of energy data protections within smart grids. Antal et al. [4] examined blockchain driven decentralized local electricity flexibility market to support small-scale prosumers to sell energy via a peer-to-peer mechanism. The authors specified an energy flexibility scheme for digitalizing prosumers flexibility to be traded on the local market as a digital asset and also deploy self-enforcing smart contracts for decentralized energy market operation. Lucas et al. [37] explored how blockchain technology can be employed to improve energy demand response service as well as tracking data sharing focusing on the authentication aspect, guaranteeing data integrity, fast registry, sharing, and origin between relevant actors.

Additionally, Marinakis et al. [38] examined how AI and data democratization can help to improve intelligent energy management. The study aimed to improve data access challenges and data sharing, algorithmic bias, privacy, transparency, and other regulatory setbacks particularly in the energy sector. Paiho et al. [43] explored cross-commodity across energy-sharing communities by providing a review of the technical situation, market, and regulation to facilitate the transition towards a distributed energy management. The study provided suggestions regarding the increasing implementation of energy sharing and how it can add to the energy transition. Wu et al. [57] carried out a review of framework for creating sustainable energy internet grounded on things-driven energy network towards services-based management system. Also, this study provided an overview of the current EI in terms of services, architecture, standards, technologies, and platforms. Petri et al. [44] investigated the use of blockchain for supporting energy sharing and trading across distributed prosumer communities. The authors further illustrated how blockchain can be used to enable the formation and usage of energy communities depicting how smart contracts can enable a more secured trading and manage energy transactions environment between producers and consumers.

Furthermore, Buth et al. [16] explored peer-to-peer energy trading based on the potential impact of blockchain to improve the decentralized and distributed local electricity markets. The article focused on how blockchain can potentially influence the configuration of the actors within the electricity system towards improving the existing system based on a social network analysis. Cheng and Yu [18] carried out a review on the use of AI based machine learning technologies to support the management, optimization, operation, dispatching, and control of electric power systems and smart energy. Kumar [34] investigated how blockchain can enable a different service within distributed energy system. Key findings from the study highlighted on problems related to emission inventory, energy sharing and trading energy generation monitoring, operating conditions, financial flows, carbon emission trading, etc. Mengelkamp et al. [39] presented a blockchain-based smart grid approach for sustainable local energy markets. The authors presented energy prosumers and consumers with a decentralized market system for trading local energy produced without the need of a third-party intermediary.

Additionally, Pop et al. [46] designed a blockchain based decentralized management of demand response approaches across smart

power grids to all the actors participating in the flexibility market. Sanseverino et al. [50] explored the deployment of blockchain within microgrids for attributing losses and transacting energy in order to have a more practical matching involving the physical state of the power grid and the resultant costs attributed to end-users. Alstone et al. [3] investigated decentralized energy systems towards clean electricity access. Findings from the study presented a conceptual and analytic framework that explained the heterogeneous continuum of centralized on-grid electricity, community grids or autonomous mini, individual, and distributed energy services. Irrespective of prior studies that have investigated distributed energy sharing and trading as reviewed in this review study. There are fewer studies that have employed the integration of IoT, AI, and DLT. Where it is important to converge IoT, AI, and DLT as this integration can improve intelligent and decentralized energy related services in promoting the energy internet in distributed energy prosumer communities. To this end this current study examines how DLT, smart contracts, and AI can enable a decentralized peer-to-peer local energy sharing and trading in distributed energy prosumer communities.

3. Method and materials

A Systematic Literature Review (SLR) was adopted in this study as the chosen research methodology. A SLR offers a structured, explicit, and rigorous procedure to identify, evaluate, and extract prior knowledge needed to explore a specific research question [32,33]. Fig. 1 depicts the SLR process employed in this current study. It consists mainly of three steps..

In the first step, relevant sources are retrieved from Web of science, Scopus, and Google scholar search engines analogous to prior studies [8, 42]. In this step keywords and terms were used to carry out the search. In the next step multiple screening and assessment was conducted to select suitable sources that contributes to provide answers to the research questions being investigated in the study. Findings present the yearly publication trends, employed methodology, the analysis of the authorship affiliated organizations country of origin and analyses of the

research areas being examined. In the final step, based on review of the literature evidence is provided on the technological convergence of AI, DLT, IoT for energy internet to decentralized and accelerate distributed energy prosumer communities. Also, in this step 3 the energy system architecture systems to decentralized and accelerate distributed energy prosumer communities is presented. Finally, the discussion, implications, and key takeaways and future directions are presented to conclude the study.

3.1. Systematic literature review process

For retrieving the relevant sources, Web of science, Scopus, and Google scholar search engines was used. The search was conducted on in August 2022 and last updated in April 2024. Corresponding to step 1 as seen in Fig. 1, keywords and semantic search strings was developed to retrieve the appropriate literature. The keywords which include Boolean

Table 1
Employed keywords and semantic search strings.

RQs	Search string
1	((“Distributed Ledger Technologies” OR “Distributed Ledger” OR “DLT” OR “Decentralized Technologies” OR “Blockchain”) AND (“Energy Data*” OR “Power Data *” OR “Electricity Data *” OR “Smart Grid*” OR “Power Grid”) *AND (“Micro Grid*” OR “Energy Grid *” OR “Energy Transactions*” OR “Electricity Transactions*”) AND (“Data Security*” OR “Data Privacy*” OR “Data Access*”) AND (“Energy Communities *” OR “Distributed Energy *” OR “Local Communities*” OR “Smart Cities*” OR “Smart Communities*” OR “Sustainable Cities*”))
2	((“Artificial Intelligence” OR “Machine Learning” OR “AI models” OR “AI Algorithms” OR “AI systems”) AND (“IoT *” OR “Internet of Things *” OR “Smart Devices *”) AND (“Energy Meters*” OR “Intelligent Sensors*” OR “Energy Internet*”) AND (“Distributed Energy Prosumer Communities *” OR “Energy Prosumers *” OR “Energy Communities *”))
3	((“Artificial Intelligence” OR “Machine Learning” OR “Distributed Ledger Technologies” OR “smart contracts” OR “Internet of Things”) AND (“Energy Sharing*” OR “Energy Internet*” OR “Energy Trading *” OR “Flexibilities *”) AND (“Energy Communities*”))

Fig. 1. SLR process employed for sources selection.

operators of “AND” and “OR” and “*” to select all related to the keyword being searched as seen in Table 1 was utilized for searching the relevant literature.

Fig. 1 depicts the selection process carried out to select studies based on the initial searched sources (as shown in from Fig. 1), 198 likely studies were retrieved from the search engines using the keywords stipulated in Table 1. 65 sources were found as duplicates and were removed. This resulted to 133 studies which titles and abstract were checked to assess if the studies discuss on issues related to technological convergence of AI, IoT, DLT, and smart contracts with energy internet to decentralized and accelerate distributed energy prosumer communities. After initial check 41 studies were removed as the content were not linked to the study area leading to 92 studies. After a quick read through the studies in relation to the research questions being examined no papers were excluded in this phase. Then, the selected 92 sources were then checked with the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Next, 36 sources were removed as they did not meet the inclusion criteria. This resulted to 56 sources. In addition, 3 studies providing guide on systematic literature review was included [32,33,56]. Thus, a total of 59 appropriate and systematically retrieved sources are utilized for this current study. Furthermore, for the inclusion and exclusion criteria the period of publications is restricted to from 2000 till date April 2024 to keep a recent focus. Although a study by Minsky [41] that first discussed on artificial intelligence was included. The language of the retrieved sources is restricted to English language only. Studies published in other languages other than English language are excluded from selection. Similarly, the source types are restricted to original research and review articles from journals, conference proceedings, technical reports, and book chapters in line with Anthony Jnr [7,42].

Journals from publishers such as Elsevier, Springer, Taylor and Francis, Wiley, etc. with high impact factors (2023) were included. For examples some of the high impact factor journals includes *Journal of Cleaner Production* (IF=9.8), *Nature climate change* (IF=30.3), *Applied Energy* (IF=10.1), *Energy Reports* (IF=4.7), *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy* (IF=8.6), *International Journal of Green Energy* (16.9), *International Journal of Energy Research* (IF=4.3), *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments* (IF=7.1), *Utilities Policy* (IF=3.8), *Energy*

Policy (IF=9.3), *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* (IF=16.3), and *Journal of Industrial Information Integration* (IF=10.4). On the contrary web links, dissertations, and unpublished works were excluded. Additionally, the included studies must be focused on emerging technologies such as AI, IoT, and DLT based systems such as blockchain and smart contracts for energy sharing and trading for energy internet for distributed energy prosumer communities or other similar contexts. Also, the study should be well grounded on a scientific approach. Lastly, the secondary data extracted from the selected sources were manually coded and entered in Microsoft Excel. Then, qualitative data analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel sheet for meta-analysis and descriptive analysis.

4. Findings

4.1. Qualitative distribution analysis

The distribution of the sources published per year (Fig. 2) indicates that research related to the integration of emerging technologies (AI, IoT, and DLT) with energy internet, energy sharing and trading and energy prosumer communities has increased over the years as seen in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 depicts the frequency of sources included in this study starting from early 2000 to 2024. The result indicates a very limited number of studies published from 2000 to 2019. The result also suggests that the number of studies related to the adoption of emerging technologies such as AI, IoT, DLT, and big data for local energy sharing and trading has increased to an average about five articles per year for the period 2018 to 2024. This publication trend reinforces that the interest of AI, IoT, DLT, smart contracts, and big data for decentralized peer-to-peer local energy sharing and trading in distributed energy prosumer communities has grown over recent years. This awareness and adoption of these emerging technologies can be justified by the usefulness of these technologies to support enable the storing of energy related data and also enable energy transactions in a secured and tamper proof manner.

Findings from Fig. 3 highlight the types of emerging technologies adopted by the selected sources included in this current study. As shown

Fig. 2. Frequency of sources included in this study.

Fig. 3. Frequency of sources by type of emerging technologies employed.

in Fig. 3 the result suggest that 19 studies employed blockchain a type of DLT in the study area, whereas 12 studies employed IoT. Also, 7 sources adopted DLT in general and big data technologies respectively, whereas 5 sources employed Information and Communications Technology (ICT) as enabler, and 3 sources employed AI technologies. However, there are limited studies that integrated AI, IoT, and DLT are reported in the literature. This indicates a need for studies that employing these emerging technologies to enable a decentralized peer-to-peer local energy sharing and trading in distributed energy prosumer communities.

Fig. 4 depicts the research method employed in the sources included in this research study. Generally, this result indicates that literature review was the most employed research methodology following the

studies that employed simulation, and case study. Then it is experiments and case study by interview. In summary literature review was the largely employed research method in converging DLT, smart contracts, and AI to enable a decentralized peer-to-peer local energy sharing and trading in distributed energy prosumer communities. However, there are fewer studies that are employed empirical driven approach. Therefore, there is need for more feasible and evidence-based research that provide practical capabilities on the potential benefits of integrating AI, IoT, and DLT with energy internet to decentralized and accelerate distributed energy prosumer communities.

Findings from Fig. 5 shows the frequency of all the publish countries of the selected sources included in this research study. The result

Fig. 4. Frequency of research methodology employed.

Fig. 5. Frequency of published sources countries.

indicates that the published sources include a total of 30 countries with an “European Union” technical report. Most of the published sources are located in China, Norway, USA, Germany, India, Italy, and UK. In summary the results reveal that the sources of the contributing authors were published in Asia, Europe, North America, and Africa.

Evidence from Fig. 6 shows the thematic analysis of research areas investigated by the selected sources. The findings indicate that most of the sources related to how DLT, smart contracts, and AI can enable a decentralized peer-to-peer local energy sharing and trading in distributed energy prosumer communities. Overall, the result as seen in Fig. 6 suggest that most studies are more aligned to general technology convergence, sustainable energy industry, smart grid to energy internet, internet of energy management, energy prosumption service, energy and transport sectors, and electric mobility. But studies mainly in the domain of distributed energy prosumer communities are limited. As such there is need for research that can contribute to this gap in knowledge.

4.2. Overview of distributed energy prosumer communities

A Distributed Energy Prosumer Communities (DEPC) typically comprises of a group of socially and geographically close energy agents. DEPC comprises of energy consumers and energy prosumers (energy

consumers that are also energy producers) can share and trade energy within their local community, provide near to real-time pricing, and also help for local balance of demand and supply. Thus, DEPC provides a distributed energy marketplace, energy pricing mechanism, and shared and inclusive market access of local RES to a specific community [39]. DEPC form a critical constituent needed to accelerate energy transition. They consist of small-scale renewable energy generators that are located within a close proximity with an energy consumption point termed as microgrid. These microgrids helps to ensure an efficient and reliable electricity distribution and transmission system. Moreover, microgrids deployed in large scale can lessen the need for expansive uneconomical energy transportation which is faced with substantial losses [48].

DEPC can support small-scale energy prosumers and consumers by providing them with more options regarding their energy supply [47]. DEPC aim to sustainably produce, supply, and utilize Distributed Energy Resources (DER) such as renewable energy sources to address societal challenges such as air pollution, energy poverty, rapid depletion of resources, and greenhouse gas emissions. Energy prosumers are active participants in addressing these challenges by generating clean electricity and energy storage systems that add flexibility to the community grid. In DEPC regular residential buildings can contribute as active energy traders that sell electricity surpluses to the local energy market thereby contributing with their energy capacity to their local

Fig. 6. Thematic analysis of research areas investigated by the selected sources.

community [44].

Additionally, this provides energy prosumers with decentralized, and controllable generation and storage solutions that enables the monetizing of energy surplus as well as partial or full independence from the smart grid. This offers economic benefits for grid operators to address the gap in energy consumption by reduce peak loads and managing demand [44]. Interconnected DEPC may provide a peer-to-peer energy sharing ecosystem backing up a nations energy

supply system. However, DEPC deployment is faced with a few challenges as seen in Fig. 7.

Although DEPC are faced with some challenges such as data security, privacy, economic, data management, energy provenance, trust management, and governance policies as shown in Fig. 7. Prior studies on energy communities mainly examined systems that is to be deployed to integrate different energy vectors needed to enhance energy efficiency. Also, these studies were focused mainly on the physical infrastructure

Fig. 7. Challenges faced in distributed energy prosumer communities.

and design needed to realize local energy systems and energy efficient. This study is limited to islanded microgrids that establishes a coherent and equilibrated energy sharing among peers within the DEPC, where it is assumed that each prosumer owns PV panels and small-scale battery energy storage (BES). Also, the energy prosumers who are the owners of distributed RESs actively participate in managing the power system's load.

This study considers the DEPC as electrical distribution systems which comprises of DER, such as distributed generators, controllable loads, or storage devices that can be coordinated and controlled, either while connected to the main grid or while islanded. Moreover, lack of proper financing both at early-stage and growth capital impedes the formation and expansion of RES initiatives. Also, complex, and often perverse policies impair the use of green technologies as compared to incumbent systems [3]. More research is needed for appropriately addressing the role of emerging technologies, existing regulations that mitigates against RES sharing and trading in DEPC [43]. As such, the deployment of DEPC requires new and innovative technologies such as big data technologies, AI, DLT, etc. [39].

4.3. Role of energy internet in distributed energy prosumer communities

The concept of Energy Internet (EI) was first suggested by Richard Buckminster Fuller during the World Game simulation within the 1970s [57]. With the rapid development of emerging technologies and sustainable energy technologies, the Energy Internet characterized by "New Energy & Internet" has advanced the new direction for technological innovation to pivot energy research and development in industries and academia (Wu and Tran, 2018). As such EI involves a complex closed-loop energy system, based on Internet and other innovative technologies [20]. Moreover, the EI allows access to different types of energy, forming openness which aims to design a new type of energy supply system with corresponding and highly integrated information and energy (Wu and Tran, 2018). The EI is important in distributed energy prosumer communities based on five key functionalities depicted in Fig. 8.

As illustrated in Fig. 8 the main importance of EI in DEPC based on the literature (Wu and Tran, 2018), are discussed below.

- The precise measurement is important in the EI as measurement provides the basis for overseeing the operational status of different energy systems deployed with distributed energy prosumer communities. It also involves identifying the source of and transparency of energy information needed to ensure that there is a consensus of trust between different actors involved in the energy generation and distribution which is lacking in the existing electrical energy system (grid).
- Widescale collaboration, cooperation, and coordination is important as the EI is characterized with wide coverage which comprises of many actors, necessitating the need for high reliability. But his collaboration is lacking in the traditional grid system. Thus, there is need for collaboration, cooperation, and coordination needed for orchestrating the operation of large-scale RES production and cooperation needed for energy transmission and usage. There is need for a common consensus among participants achieve via coordination to achieve maximum profits.
- Automated and intelligent energy management, control, and optimization involves employed big data analysis and AI based algorithms to provide technical support for the EI to handle different distributed energy sources within distributed energy prosumer communities. This is not carried out in the traditional grid system. The energy life cycle which comprises of energy production, distribution, and consumption mainly relies on intelligent systems which are employed to achieve efficient and flexible energy conversion and optimization of electricity transmission path, in so doing improving the energy system's operational reliability and efficiency.
- Open energy trading is one of the focuses of EI as this is important for providing future energy systems, including integrating large-scale legacy power grids and distributed micro grids deployed in distributed energy prosumer communities. This will enable energy access for all citizen thereby reducing energy poverty as well as supporting different energy services such as demand response, ancillary

Fig. 8. Significance of EI in distributed energy prosumer communities.

services, and energy trading. This will help to reduce the peaks and valleys of the EI, thus improving the operational efficiency which is needed in traditional grid systems.

- Democratized and inclusive energy supply and demand for citizens will enable an energy as a service ecosystem which provide energy to all without prejudice. Energy prosumers can also be energy consumers, thereby fostering energy community initiatives towards citizen-centered energy policies which is needed in the existing electrical energy system (grid) [29].

Overall, the goal of EI is to deliver a flexible Plug and Play energy access and consumption energy as a service ecosystem for bidirectional power flow and seamless integration as well as data interfacing flow-based energy network for open trading, and optimized services for sustainable development [57]. Similarly, researchers such as Huang et al. [27]; Bao et al. [14] highlighted that the EI forms a novel power grid configuration based on the Internet and energy storage technologies. Also, Hua et al. (2021) provided a data-driven dynamical control aimed at bottom-up energy internet system. In distributed energy prosumer communities EI can be applied to manage the production of RES and optimization of the entire energy supply system. Although researchers such as Hua et al. (2024) proposed an optimal dispatch for multiple interconnected-integrated energy systems based on a multi-energy interaction and aggregated demand response across multiple stakeholders. Distributed energy prosumer communities are faced with many challenges as shown in Fig. 7, such as the data security and privacy issues faced due to the adoption of centralized energy management system [43]. Accordingly, most energy management systems are now migrating toward a distributed configuration, hence the traditional centralized management architecture is undoubtedly no longer applicable [14].

Additionally, the EI involves more types of energy and participants, as the availability of information and energy are closely connected, which poses challenges such as how to sustainably manage and control the operation of distributed energy prosumer communities [30]. Although the deployment of EI is particularly complex, hence it requires high penetration of heterogeneous resources and deep integration from different domains, where each domain also entails a wide range of emerging technologies [57]. As such, research on the EI is still at the architecture design and theoretical level. Thus, there is need to explore how emerging technologies can help in the design and operationalization of the Energy Internet (Wu and Tran, 2018). With the adoption of emerging technologies such as DLT the EI has rapidly developed. As DLT supports energy management, sharing, trading, tracing, tracking, etc. in distributed energy prosumer communities has been greatly improved [14]. EI envisions a future energy community where the sustainable concerns of the environment, economy, citizens, and efficiency is achieved via provision of digitalized data-driven energy services, the flexibility of multi-energy systems, and the interaction of citizen-centred energy policies. Analogous to prior study [43], evidence from this study provides an energy system architecture as a multi-disciplinary framework in terms of architectural model, technologies, infrastructures, standards, services, and systems.

4.4. Challenges faced in distributed prosumer energy communities

Electricity is the delivery of energy as a result of transmission across different levels within the power grid. It involves the interaction of various entities across respective connected infrastructures [57]. As the society becomes more connected and digitalized the reliance on energy has progressively increased over the years. Evidence from a report by the BP Statistical Review of World Energy as cited by Bao et al. [14] suggested that the global primary energy demand increased by 2.9 percent within 2018. Simultaneously there was a 2.0 percent increase in carbon emissions associated with energy consumption from energy sources not generated from RES. To curb such environmental issues linked to carbon

emissions, prosumers have evolved where energy is generated from renewable energy sources such as solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind energy. For example, in residential areas homeowners can install solar PV electricity generation system in their buildings for self-use, and excess or surplus electricity can be shared with to the power grid for financial rebates (i.e. thereby consumers become prosumers). But energy prosumer communities are faced with several challenges such as the management of dynamic and large number of prosumers.

The conventional grid typically deploys a centralized management system, which is not scalable for managing large number of prosumers. Moreover, energy prosumers are faced with associated cost incurred for maintenance and management of conventional centralized-based infrastructure, which has resulted to operational challenges caused by lack of common standards or different technologies which results to a lack of mutual trust among members of the energy community [45]. Additionally, the consumption of RES and deployment of smart meters in energy communities will enable a bidirectional energy trading which in turn requires an efficient mechanism for scheduling energy exchange and strategies to be employed for distributing incentives to energy prosumers. Similarly, the current energy market operations mostly rely on a main authority which makes this approach prone to a single point of failure, data security, and privacy issues [40]. This requires the design of a sustainable, fair, safe, interoperable, and efficient smart grid system. Also, this design needs to consider increasing use of electric cars which may have an impact on the operation of future smart grid system [14]. Moreover, there is a tradeoff between preserving privacy and confidentiality and enhancing interpretability of data [49]. As such this study advocated the need for the design of distributed energy prosumer communities. Hence, there is need for a decentralized architecture that enables the exchange of electricity among energy consumers and prosumers in an effective, secure, and autonomous approach without the participation of a third-party authorization.

4.5. Applicability of DLT in distributed prosumer energy communities

Distributed energy prosumer communities can promote clean energy production and consumption initiatives in addition to fostering citizens' participation which in turn aim at increasing and optimizing the sharing and utilization of local energy resources [44]. DEPC have the potential to enable and dynamically engage small-scale energy prosumers by facilitating decentralized, interconnected, and smart energy markets thereby supporting the strategic agenda set by the European Commission [16]. In open markets such as distributed prosumer energy communities, it is essential for an energy consumers and prosumer to be provided with added value by monetizing energy service or product [44]. To operate in an automated and intelligent way DEPC require the deployment of emerging technologies that not only facilitates near real-time generation, balancing, sharing, trading, transmission, and pricing of RES in a secure and sustainable way [16]. Likewise, to support the actualization of distributed energy prosumer communities the International Energy Agency (<https://www.iea.org/reports/digitalisation-and-energy>), mentioned that the adoption of novel technologies in the energy sector can increase flexibility and enable integration across the entire energy systems [43]. But energy consumer and prosumer are faced with data security and privacy issues due to centralized architecture deployed in existing energy systems in energy communities.

Over the decades the DEPC has become more distributed resulting to some challenges that needs to be resolved, such as distributed control, storage, trading, management, etc. These issues cannot be effectively addressed by traditional energy systems, thus DLT is proposed as a solution to address some of these aforementioned shortcomings [5,14]. DLT which is an emerging technology has been used in different domains such as in finance, trading, supply chain, health, education, energy, etc. [8], to manage the distribution, exchange, and storage of data between participants either based on a public, private, or consortium-based networks (also referred to as permissioned or

federated) [9,22]. DLT is simply a database that is used to store and locate data or transactions across user nodes geographically distributed across different locations. Each computer user within the network is referred to as a node user. DLT essentially can be seen as a shared datasheets maintained across several distributed nodes [22].

DLT is adopted as an alternative as it is based on a decentralized architecture as compared to the centralized architecture employed for example by cloud computing which are faced with issues such as a single point of failure, cyber security attacks, data privacy, and tampering. DLT employs decentralized method for securely and privately storing and sharing data. It excludes the need for a third-party authorization through the deployment of a P2P communication interface and protocols, using consensus mechanisms and cryptographic algorithms [52]. To validate and add a new data or transaction within a distributed ledger, a consensus mechanism is made among the network nodes. A data is added only if a particular number of nodes users agree. There are different protocols or consensus mechanisms to are being adopted in DLT. A few examples of these consensus mechanisms include Proof of Stake (PoS), Proof of Work (PoW), Proof of Elapsed Time (PoET), Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance (PBFT), etc. [52]. DLT is suitable to be adopted in DEPC based on certain characteristics as presented in Fig. 9.

Based on some characteristics of DLT as shown in Fig. 9, DLT is generally regarded to enable the disintermediation and decentralization of transaction or data among different parties across a global scale [16]. DLT can be applied to distributed prosumer energy communities enables P2P trading of energy, which eliminates the need for a middle accounting authority such as the traditional energy utility company. Compared to the conventional energy trading approach, where a central control system solely processes all the measured energy related data from distributed energy prosumers, DLT can accelerate energy transactions, by avoiding single point failure, and further prevent data manipulation from any participant [36]. Also, DLT can incentivize citizens via a sharing economy approach thus offering greater options for both energy prosumer and consumers while enabling a much better flexibility as compared to the offerings provided by the existing market [44]. Such sharing economy approach has the possibility to decentralize clean energy production but can also balance electricity consumption from energy consumers by not being restricted to price constraints or energy services from a sole energy provider. DLT can offer the mechanisms needed to facilitate energy resources decentralization.

In particular, energy services providers can use DLT based smart contracts for transfer of energy as a resource and also support the

tracking of energy being consumed or purchased by energy consumers [44]. Moreover, smart contracts can be deployed to automatic bidding, real-time metering, negotiation, and enable switching of energy supplier in a transparent manner with limited human involvement. This can be financially beneficial to energy consumers by providing more competitive and less monopolistic environment for energy producers [36]. Although many citizens receive their electricity from big energy provider, but the development in decentralized energy production from sources such as solar and wind, enables citizens to generate their own energy as prosumers. As such technological developments on smart meters can contribute to help homeowners to save, transfer, and sell excess energy to other residents based on a DLT-based agreements [44]. As such over the last few years DLT has been seen as an enabler for the conceptualization and execution of new energy approaches such as P2P energy trading, but there is fewer research on the formation of the actors in DEPC and its ability to change the existing energy sharing system [16].

4.5.1. Actors in distributed energy prosumer communities

The dynamics and connectivity in the electricity system have given rise to the organization of different actors in DEPC. The main actors involved in the DEPC are described below. Overall, the main actors comprise of the aggregator, balance responsible party/trader, charge point operator/market service provider, consumer/prosumer, data facilitator, distribution system operator, market operator, metering company, producer, supplier, and transmission system operator as suggested in the literature [16].

- a) **Electricity producers**-The electricity producers are important in the electricity system, and they encompass to some extent energy prosumers. They are responsible for the energy generation process in distributed energy prosumer communities. The electricity producers are mostly businesses that may or may not be part of big energy corporations. The energy generated by electricity producers are often sold to the power grid as such they are in direct contact with power grid operators, who communicate with the electricity producers on the required amount of electricity that is needed for grid balancing.
- b) **Market operator**- To trade generated energy to the power grid, electricity producers often make rely on the electricity market-places, which are managed by the market operator. In countries like Norway the market operator is Statnett who is responsible for guaranteeing that the energy system is continuously in balance by

Fig. 9. Characteristics of DLT for distributed energy prosumer communities.

ensuring that there is a prompt balance between the consumption and production of electricity within Norway. The electricity can either be sold to large consumers, suppliers, or traders (who then deliver the energy to small and medium sized energy consumers). The market operator is responsible for the administration and management of electricity trade and payment among customers, suppliers, and producers towards the creation of a transparent and fair price mechanism. Also, the market operator ensures the delivery and payment of energy related transactions. To achieve a properly functioning power grid it is critical that electricity can be securely transported across long distances and that the balance between electricity demand and supply is maintained.

- c) **Transmission System Operator (TSO)**- The TSO is tasked with maintaining and operating the high voltage grid. Similarly, Statnett is also the TSO in Norway, and it owns the energy transmission grid across Norway. The TSO manages the transmission process of electricity, by monitoring the electricity transmission network, the electricity import capacity, and the overall balancing of the power grid. For balancing of the power the grid, the TSO cannot operate on its own as such it communicates with other parties that regulates the inflow of electricity for grid balancing, for example with energy producers and with the distribution system operator for electricity network management.
- d) **Balance Responsible Party (BRP)/Trader**- A Balance Responsible Party (BRP)/Trader is tasked for balancing the sales and acquisition volume of electricity as well as the planning of the daily energy usage. BRP must put forward their e-programs at the end of the day to the TSO to enable the balancing of the grid. While the traders do not only buy and sell energy but are not responsible for the energy price risk. The TSO communicates another actor which is the Balance Responsible Party/Trader who is responsible to predict and compute how much electricity each party (producer) connected to the power grid is going to feed/supply into and take out/demand from the power grid.
- e) **Distribution System Operator (DSO)**- Where the TSO is responsible for the operation and management of the high voltage grid, the Distribution System Operator (DSO) is responsible for operating and providing low and medium voltage grids across the regional distribution of electricity. There are almost 130 DSOs within Norway, tasked for operating and managing the regional and distribution grids. Additionally, the DSO is tasked for reactive power management and voltage control within the grid. Due to these responsibilities the DSOs must communicate and interact with other actors involved in the grid, for example with energy market service providers/charge point operators for electricity flow to charging stations for EVs, with electricity metering enterprises for real time updates on energy utilization for consumers, and BRP/traders for electricity distribution that is supplied within the electricity market.
- f) **Energy consumers and prosumers**- Another actor are the energy consumers and prosumers which are usually the final actors in the process of electricity supply. The energy consumer is an end user or individual who purchases and consumes electricity, whereas the prosumer both purchase and produces energy, e.g. through privately owned rooftop PV solar panels.
- g) **Suppliers**- Since energy producers often sell their energy to the marketplace and not directly to energy consumers, these energy consumers require another actor to procure electricity from. The suppliers mainly interact with the market operator for purchase of electricity, with another actor who is the data facilitator who communicates the actual energy consumption data and also considering the energy consumer. Thus, the supplier delivers electricity to energy consumer or prosumer.
- h) **Data facilitator**- The data facilitator emerged in response to the increasing amount of data produced among the different actors

involved in the electricity system. In Norway the data facilitator is called Elhub (elhub.no). The data facilitator expedites the availability and exchange of data between electricity market parties, such as smart metering companies, system operators, BRP, and suppliers. Also, the data facilitator promotes a free electricity market processes by providing an administrative system for energy consumers and suppliers which facilitates the switching of suppliers for energy consumers.

- i) **Metering company**- The smart metering company is an actor who works closely with the data facilitator. The smart metering companies previously was part of the grid operators but are now a separate entity. The smart metering company install, supply, and maintain the electricity and other utility such as water meter, gas meter, by collecting electricity, water, and gas usage data which is sent to the data facilitator.
- j) **Aggregators**- The increased need for flexibility across the grid necessitates the need for aggregators who possess the capability to manage demand response and provide economic or technical services to the electricity actors. Aggregators allow flexible management of the grid by rewarding or providing incentives to energy consumers who decrease their energy demand from the grid at peak times.
- k) **Charge Point Operators**- The charge point operators are actors responsible for the instalment, delivery, and maintenance of Electric Vehicles (EV) charging points.
- l) **Mobility service providers**- Similarly, mobility service providers are responsible for the business aspects of mobility related products and services for EVs including subscriptions, usage, and payments for EV charging. It is common since charge point operator and market service provider fulfill the roles for each actor.
- m) **National and international bodies**-There are national and international bodies who regulate and supervise both national and international electricity market, but nonetheless who are not active in the electricity market. This parties are responsible for safeguarding a competition-friendly market and protecting the national consumer interests. They include the regulatory body who is the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E) aimed to set up a formidable European energy market to support the European energy and climate agenda.

4.6. DLT based local energy markets in distributed energy prosumer communities

Distributed energy prosumer communities are now deploying Local Energy Markets (LEM) which are geographically controlled market mechanisms with different pricing mechanisms between interconnected actors such as energy producers, consumers, and prosumers [6]. These actors are involved in either or both the generation and demand of energy based on a pre-defined time slot. The market mechanism employed in LEM enables energy sharing and trading between the actor's participation in the distributed energy prosumer communities [39]. Thus, LEM are simply market platforms that provide energy producers, consumers, and prosumers with the possibility to virtually exchange energy within their local community [39]. This energy exchange mostly aims to empower the local community by providing possible energy cost saving, by increasing the local economy by providing revenues which may foster further investments for local RES generation in distributed energy prosumer communities. Accordingly, the deployment of LEM can help in improving energy flows in DEPC via prosumers' energy supply which helps for energy balance ultimately contributing to the EU target of becoming a climate neutral continent by 2050.

In LEM, energy prosumers can adjust their energy profiles based on their flexibility and also trade their energy flexibility in advance by negotiating better energy prices [11]. Energy prosumers can as well

empower DEPC to take control and ownership of their energy system and also contribute to scalability and resilience. Consequently, more RES will be utilized locally thereby minimizing the amount of electricity to be transported on longer distances promoting local optimization of electricity flows [4]. Presently, energy trading is mostly done in energy communities using a centralized marketplace model, DLT can be employed as a substitute to run a decentralized marketplace model based on a distributed financial system. Although many studies on LEM models already exist in the literature, there are limited studies that utilize DLTs such as blockchain as enable to provide a decentralized energy market platform [39]. Since LEM are constrained to their local community or geographical locality, it is rational to use private and permissioned based DLT which will restrict access to the local energy market to only members of the distributed energy prosumer communities [39].

Although research is still developing in use of DLT to improve local energy market, a few industrial projects are now being implemented and evaluated to assess the deployment of DLTs such as blockchains (Ethereum) to support energy marketplaces such as the Brooklyn Microgrid (<https://www.brooklyn.energy/>). Also, the energy market mechanism being tested in Brooklyn Microgrid is deployed via a smart contract implemented on a private DLT to ease financial transactions such as in digital currency exchanges maybe from cryptocurrency to other currencies e.g. Euros (€) [36,39]. Additionally, a few businesses have set platforms to support energy exchange to aggregate sellers and buyers. For instance, the Dutch corporation Vandebroon (<https://vandebroon.nl/>), offers the opportunity to buy clean energy directly from energy producers utilizing a central party that manages the energy network, generates bills, and checks the balance between energy production and consumption.

Besides, other incentivization platform based on DLT across distributed energy prosumer communities includes SolarCoin (<https://solarcoin.org/>), which aimed at providing financial benefits for energy prosumers with solar PV systems generation. SolarCoin gives solar energy prosumers one virtual token termed as SolarCoin for each Megawatt of solar energy generated. The virtual token can be utilized like cryptocurrencies for buying and trading of goods as well as services [36]. Another good example is the Sunexchange (<https://thesunexchange.com>), which offers a business prospect for energy prosumers of solar PV systems. A DLT based leasing or sharing system is employed to automatically share the energy prosumers generated energy to energy consumers, while energy prosumers are remunerated with Bitcoins or an equivalent sum of local currency for the shared solar energy (Sunexchange, 2019). However, researchers such as Buth et al. [16] highlighted that the deployment of emerging technology, such as DLT based blockchain in electricity system may be faced with different challenges such as how to manage the role and responsibilities of actors such as TSO, DSO, etc. within the distributed energy prosumer communities. Accordingly, due to existing actors in distributed energy prosumer communities poses challenges to the adoption of DLT in the energy system as DLT will decrease the number of actors needed within the distributed energy prosumer communities [16].

4.6.1. AI as enabler to accelerate distributed energy prosumer communities

The notion of AI has been discussed since the year 1940 but was formally outlined around 1960 [41]. AI refers to intelligence exhibited by machines [28]. It is a scientific field mainly in computer science which focuses on the study of autonomous systems. Over the years, AI has been well employed across different sectors. AI aims to enable computer systems to learn from experience thereby enabling computers to execute tasks which they are not explicitly programmed to perform [43]. AI have been applied to a wide variety of domains and industries ranging from healthcare, autonomous cars, to smart cities and smart grids. AI is now used in energy system management and power grid [7]. This includes forecasting and modelling of demand-side resources such as RES from solar PV and windmills. Moreover, AI provide a medium for

optimizing and automating energy management, enabling energy consumers and prosumers to become key actors within the local energy systems [12]. AI can help to automated energy management, supervision existing energy market structures and incentivization mechanisms [43]. AI can enable intelligent control and management of flexible energy resources to foster active participation of prosumers within the (local) energy markets via automated trading of green energy and flexibility [43].

AI-based ML forecasting models have been employed to predict how much energy is needed to be generated for consumers within a short-term, medium-term, and long-term [1]. With the generation of real-time data and advancement in IoT devices and sensors, AI algorithms are being developed to analyze these data to provide value added information [52]. As reported in the literature Rusitschka and Curry [49] described on how AI based ML algorithm can be employed to compute the price of the electricity by processing and analyzing the generated load data of different energy types using advanced data analytics. The author employed data from different sources such as live market data, power grid data, current weather, and operational data from virtual power plant. Although AI has been adopted in distributed energy prosumer communities for cross-commodity and decentralized energy management. AI is faced with challenges such as lack of data and data quality, risks, ethics, or legal concerns and compliance issues, lack of qualified experts, availability of technical infrastructure, integration challenges, due to the increased complexity and issues in managing different infrastructures [1,43].

4.7. The role of IoT to accelerate distributed energy prosumer communities

The Internet of Things (IoT) is term used to define the linking of things connected to the Internet [43]. IoT as a term was first mentioned in the literature in 2009 [13], to describe an approach that supports physical objects to share information with other objects or users. IoT are mostly remotely controlled and automatically execute their functions. The IoT architecture is usually supported by components such as simple low-cost micro-controllers equipped with batteries, and embedded in sensors, software, actuators, and communication technologies, mostly wireless. IoT depends on Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) as an enabling technology, where RFID is simply a wireless based system that consists of two devices: readers and tags. The reader is a component that has one or more physical antennas that produce radio waves and receive transmitting signals back from the tag. RFID usually deploy reactive tags which is comprises of a physical chip, with a corresponding code number, and antennas required to transmit data to a specific radio base [25].

These RFID tags can transmit data at a relative distance and the radio base can simultaneously interpret several tags. In distributed energy prosumer communities, tags can be deployed for passive sensing of temperature, wind, humidity, pressure, etc. [2]. Similarly, Near Field Communication (NFC) is another substitute technology recommended for identification of devices among IoT devices. NFC is an improved and newer type of RFID technology but is more resistant to communication interference. As such has been recently implemented in smartphones which are equipped with NFC readers that can be used to control applications. Analogous to RFID, NFC can help to automatically identify product, preventing input errors. In deploying IoT in any environment the Single Board Computers (SBCs) are the vital part of IoT device. Thus, SBC is a complete computer assembled on a single circuit board, comprising microprocessor(s), input/output, memory, and other features necessary to have a functional computer. Also, SBC are normally built for demonstrating development systems or used as embedded computer controllers. Popular SBC devices include Raspberry, Arduino, and ESP32. SBC devices can monitor luminosity, temperature, or other physical scales using SBC, e.g. as a switch to automatically turn on/off charging stations for EV fleets [10].

For example, SBC devices can support real-time monitoring of energy

produced and consumed, in addition to actuating on triggering when to exchange energy among energy prosumers and consumers [2]. SBC devices can be connected with advanced metering infrastructure (AMI) and smart meters (SM) which generates enormous amount of data [35], that can be used to manage and control energy sharing and trading towards accelerating distributed energy prosumer communities [12]. Therefore, using IoT devices the amount of energy shared and traded by energy prosumers can be recorded by smart metering devices and can be made accessible by the data owners or data producers [35]. Moreover, data such as energy consumption and current level, odometers, EV location, and so on, can also be gathered using IoT devices. These real-time data can be conveyed using different communication technologies, such as LTE, 5G/6 G, LoRaWAN, SigFox, Wi-Fi, Wi-Max, Zig-bee, Bluetooth, 3GPP standards, Dedicated short-range communications (DSRC), fiber optics, Power Line Communication (PLC), copper wire6LoWPAN, and others, in relation to throughput, distance, and latency requirements [40,52].

4.8. Convergence of AI with DLT based IoT for energy exchange in DEPC

In distributed energy prosumer communities' energy is generally generated in a decentral approach by small-scale local energy producers who may own a wind turbine or install solar panels on their roofs. DLT based systems can be deployed to enable possible small-scale participants, such as energy prosumers, Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SME), and energy consumers to trade energy with each other based on a peer-to-peer trading mechanism. As mentioned in the literature [16], to achieve this a local energy market will emerge within a local community grid, where energy consumers and energy prosumers can share and trade energy within their local community. Likewise, DLT can be utilized in energy markets to trading RES between residents and incentivization of energy prosumers leading to the formation of a much-secured energy prosumer communities. DLT can facilitate a near real-time energy pricing as well as a local balance of energy demand and supply. Overall, these local markets are automated, decentralized and seamlessly interconnected to energy consumers and prosumers through virtual power plants or their local microgrids [21]. Additionally, there will be need for institutional change to support the legitimation of energy trading within distributed energy prosumer communities to strengthens the roles of energy prosumer. Each resident who is an energy prosumer is equipped with a smart meter and a battery, that enables bilateral sharing and trading of energy stored on the battery [16].

AI can improve energy sharing thereby significantly providing resource savings and AI can also provide a reliable solution for real-time monitoring for energy production and consumption. AI can be employed to automatically match energy demand for electricity dispatch planning [31]. This can be realized by adaptive grid dispatch and efficient operation, ensuring that all of the electricity supply and consumption flow are controlled via automatic balance of demand and supply, ensuring automatic energy trading for safe and transparent optimization of distributed energy generation for demand side management. AI can help to determine the distribution, processing, and optimum configuration of electricity supply to improve operational efficiency improving the consumption rate of RES, optimization, and operation of the microgrid [58]. The convergence of AI with DLT and IoT based system can facilitate automatic energy sharing and trading by facilitating micro transactions via AI based algorithms and DLT based smart contracts [16]. The application of DLT and AI has also been surveyed in the literature for decentralized infrastructure in addressing challenges, such as improved data security, consensus protocols, scalability, trusted oracles, and standardization. For instance, SingularityNET is an open-source platform based on DLT based smart contracts employed as a decentralized marketplace for coordination of AI services, aimed for the creation, sharing, and monetize of decentralized AI services at scale [52]

Buth et al. [16] mentioned that for DLT such as blockchain to properly function in enabling energy trading, there is need to integrate

DLT with advanced algorithms as such AI is converged with DLT to facilitate local energy trading towards the actualization of distributed energy prosumer communities. The convergence of AI with DLT can help to manage the generation and optimization of the energy distribution networks across the distributed energy prosumer communities [16]. The integration of DLT with IoT has been previously researched to provide benefits such as fine-access control, data trustworthiness, coordination of identity and legitimacy, and decentralized infrastructure, in addition to data accountability, immutability, and transparency [52]. DLT based IoT can enable electrical devices such as smart electricity meters to measure the charge and discharge of electricity using tamper-proof data transmission. DLT can support residents to obtain real-time information of the micro grid, and each node user can extract information on their energy usage [58]. Practically there is need for a new stakeholder or an existing stakeholder that will be responsible for the management and governance of the AI, DLT, and IoT infrastructure [5]. As such in future electricity system across distributed energy prosumer communities an entirely novel actor with central authority may but the issue is who will govern the usage of AI, DLT and IoT infrastructures.

4.8.1. Developed energy system architecture

This article explores how emerging technologies (AI and DLT based IoT), can influence the operationalization and actualization of the green energy transition in cities and communities. In this article an energy system architecture is developed based on the energy internet concept and the microgrid. As suggested in the literature [17] the developed energy system architecture comprises of the five layers supported by the technology convergence of AI, DLT, and smart contracts as seen in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10 demonstrates the five main layers of the energy system architecture. The related component within each layer is derived from the literature [43,44,58,59]. Each of the layers for the energy system architecture are discussed in Table 2.

As seen in Fig. 10 the use of AI and DLT in the architecture connects key stakeholders such as the energy prosumers, DSOs, TSOs, aggregators, retailers/suppliers, etc. to collaborate through a decentralized based approach to fully support a distributed electricity demand and generation matching to ensure stable power grid operation in distributed energy prosumer communities. The technological convergence of AI, DLT, and IoT can revolutionize the microgrids across the globe by reducing the manual work, associated risks, estimate the energy demands, and improve energy data management. In the developed energy system architecture, AI, DLT, and smart contracts enables the functioning of a community microgrids to orchestrate the generation of energy directly from RES and aid energy prosumers to trade surplus directly to their neighbors in a more secure, transparent, fair, and distributed way. This helps to decrease the electricity bill for citizens, fosters green energy, decrease the cost of electricity (as the availability of surplus energy will lead to reduce demand for energy), and provides incentives to energy prosumers who trade kilowatt of energy per-unit [35].

By deploying smart contracts energy consumers can select the type and origin of energy they prefer in a dynamic manner [16]. Moreover, smart contracts enable machine-to-machine communication for IoT devices used within residential areas which are connected to the power grid through smart meters. Also, EV users that are connected to the power grid via plug can autonomously charge their EV based on the pre-defined time set for charging when energy price is lower [16]. A key challenge in energy exchange is how to design an effective and flexible sharing and trading mechanism to realize the efficient allocation of RES. The conventional centralized trading scheme fair is faced with long decision-making time and low efficiency. The P2P energy trading and sharing mode supported by DLT can enable participants in energy market for self-management operation through an intelligent mechanism so as to improve the operation of the distributed energy prosumer communities [58].

Fig. 10. Developed energy system architecture.

Table 2
Presented architecture layers for the energy system architecture.

Layers	Description
Business	This layer includes business view on available information exchange within the energy marketplace. This layer captures the market structure and energy business models, regulatory structures, and policies, incentivization schemes for energy prosumers, pricing mechanisms for energy trading, and business portfolios of energy products and services for all market parties involved in energy trading in distributed energy prosumer communities.
Function	This layer describes energy related business services and procedures. The functions are solely based on actors and physical deployment needed in systems, applications/digital platforms, and components. Also, this layer supports energy prosumers to make decision using emerging technologies such as AI, DLT, IoT, etc. to facilitate decentralized energy marketplaces. Within the functions are derived by accessing the functionality needed to achieve distributed energy prosumer communities.
Information	This layer mainly describes the data needed to improve the current energy business process needed for achieving distributed energy prosumer communities. This layer also captures data that is being employed and exchanged between different energy systems. These data enable an interoperable and decentralized energy sharing system.
Communication	This layer captures the wireless and wired protocols and interfaces required to achieve seamless interoperable exchange of data between different actors, systems, physical infrastructure, and electrical components for energy sharing and trading.
Component	This layer comprises of the IoT physical devices, energy distribution and basic connectivity needed for running of distributed energy prosumer communities. This includes protection equipment and tele-control devices, network infrastructure (switches, routers, servers, etc.), and other computer systems.

The architecture as a framework leverages DLT based smart contracts to support decentralization of electricity supply and demand within an energy sharing and trading marketplace. The use of smart contracts also focuses to protect energy consumers and prosumers from privacy violations and data security addresses some key requirements of GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation). In the existing centralized application achieving interoperability and integration of energy related data

collected from heterogeneous IoT devices (as hard infrastructures), and distributed RES is challenging. But using DLT data can be acquired from the heterogeneous IoT devices can be locally stored within the DLT as data transactions and replicated for across to the node users [46]. Therefore, within the distributed energy prosumer communities DLT is deployed and IoT devices such as energy metering devices produces data which registers energy production or consumption values saved to distributed ledger.

The self-enforcing smart contracts are pre-defined and employed for energy demand flexibility and demand response events, as well as incentivization and fees rates, as well as polices for balancing energy production with the energy demand. As such the smart contracts are defined in a distributed manner at the level of each RES that is registered within the distributed energy prosumer communities for demand response event to specify the required energy demand and tunings to the required energy baseline. Smart contracts can help to evaluate demand response by assessing the difference between the predicted energy curve and actual observed energy values. If substantial deviations are observed, pre-defined actions are suggested to be taken to rebalance the electricity demand with the energy production, making smart contracts to act as a decentralized control governance mechanism. The smart contracts can be implemented using Solidity language (<https://docs.soliditylang.org/en/develop/>), which is a Turing complete based contract-oriented programming language.

4.9. Use case on applicability of DLT and AI to support microgrid operations

The use of RES in DEPC can contribute to socioeconomic growth and environment sustainability. Microgrids embodies in general an effective electricity transmission and distribution system, effectively making use of existing electricity infrastructures. Findings from the literature argued that the deployment of microgrids in energy communities have been helped to decrease costs concerning energy generation, mitigating power outages or blackouts, improving operational costs for distribution and transmission, and lessening CO₂ emissions. However, future communities will need to be decentralized to effectively manage the exchange of energy based on a P2P method. This necessitates the need for governing the transmission and distribution of RES to satisfy the energy

need of consumers [48]. In DEPC microgrid enable distributed energy markets to foster the connection of small-scale energy prosumers and consumers to trade and share locally produced green energy. Hence, microgrids fosters the consumption of electricity close to its generation and, consequently, foster the effective use of local resources and sustainability [37]. Although, the deployment of microgrids in DEPC requires investment or financing for aggregation, it provides a relatively low minimal cost to energy prosumers and at times requires a population density of participants. Thus, it also requires local political decisions as well as community support from the local community [3].

The adoption of the energy system architecture (enabled by DLT and AI), can accelerate the development of DEPC by connecting existing transmission networks with RES to supply energy consumers with low-carbon electricity that increase energy resilience, reduces energy poverty, and foster operational flexibility [48]. For example, a DLT-based microgrid network nodes can promote the consensual sharing and synchronizing of data across energy communities by connecting to energy metering devices. Participating node within the microgrid can each access shared information across the network and also retain an identical copy of the distributed data [48]. In the microgrid AI can provide security services related with agreements between power grid operators, energy prosumers, and consumer deploying smart contracts which helps to decrease the overhead of monetary cost and time thereby reducing human mistakes and increasing service reliability. In the developed energy system architecture, DLT stores energy consumption and production data collected from intelligent metering devices and smart sensors using a tamper proof approach. Then self-enforcing smart contracts programmatically defines the anticipated energy flexibility for energy prosumers and consumer, thus establishing the AI based conditions for balancing energy demand with energy production at micro grid level, subsequently keeping the power grid system stable.

DLT provides a transparent and trustworthy means for advancing green energy usage and minimizing energy waste in a controllable and flexible way. For example, DLT can trace and track data transactions across the network and thus can be employed to source the origin of every unit of electrical energy. From a user-centred perspective this enables an energy consumer to select what type of energy he/she wants to utilize (for instance, from which source he/she wants to buy the electricity), as specified in their energy contract which is saved within smart contract. By employing DLT, privacy-sensitive data, such as the prosumer's type of electrical equipment, the value/reading of meters, and its topographical position is encrypted and/or substituted with a public key, which is stored and exchanged via the DLT platform. More importantly, electricity transactions of energy consumer and prosumer, i.e., the quantity and type of energy produced or consumed is stored within the DLT [48]. To maintain the stability of the power grid, a dynamic electricity pricing mechanism is employed in the energy system architecture, where the price varies based on the type of electricity produced and supplied to the power grid. Moreover, each consumer has an "digital wallet", where the user automatically exchanging transactions with energy prosumer and grid operator within the DLT.

Thus, information of each unit (kWh) of electricity produced or consumed by an energy consumer/prosumer is transparent enabling the user to trace and track back every unit of electricity to where it is generated. Also, the amount of electricity delivery can be verified by transmitting the coded kilowatt hour to the energy consumer's "digital wallet" [48]. In practice, the grid stability and dynamic price can also be attained via the use of load aggregation and intelligent storage. During high energy generation and consequently low energy prices, small scale batteries can store up energy which can be feed back to the microgrid when energy production is low and when there is high demand and high electricity prices. The electricity can be supplied from the prosumers batteries thereby reducing and stabilizing the load on the power grid. Also, energy prosumer as the owners of the batteries can receive incentives in their "digital wallet" through smart contract that enables

flexible pricing and prosumer payments based on pre-set user preferences selected within the smart contracts. A battery management system can be installed in residential buildings with or without a PV solar system that seamlessly connects with the smart metering devices within the energy community. In addition, the stability of the power grid can also be attained by demand response which controls the usage of electricity. For example, the charging of EV fleets within the community can be switched on when the energy demand is low and can be switched off when the peak demand is high. By aggregating and controlling different types of electrical equipment with the help of smart contract and dynamic energy pricing, a balance can be achieved for energy demand and supply towards load stability across the power grid can be maintained [48].

5. Discussion and implications

5.1. Discussion

The digitalization of the energy sector via the adoption of emerging technologies such as DLT, IoT, and AI are paving the way for innovative energy models. This study develops an energy system architecture to enable the sharing and trading of RES grounded on the sharing economy principles to unlock the energy sharing and trading activities for energy prosumer and consumers in distributed energy prosumer communities. The energy system architecture is based on a DLT based smart contracts driven peer-to-peer sharing architecture that allows each energy node to determine which energy node to share and trade (sell to or buy from) based on the user's preference (such as a specific energy type, minimum costs, most reliable energy supply, etc.). The peer-to-peer sharing energy sharing and trading is supported by DLT based smart contracts that facilitates energy exchanges between energy nodes while also enabling the control and monitoring of the entire energy distribution network within the distributed energy prosumer communities.

Findings from this study reveals that IoT can supports for real-time monitoring and control of energy management system. AI technologies can aid to automate decision-making towards ensuring optimal control of RES. Evidence from this article also provides multidisciplinary research that support in designing effective and intelligent energy trading platforms applicable in distributed energy prosumer communities. Findings from this article contributes towards the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 7 which aims to promote an affordable and clean energy by decreasing energy poverty, SDG 9 industry, innovation, and infrastructure by employing DLT, IoT, and AI to decentralized and accelerate distributed energy prosumer communities, SDG 11 promoting sustainable cities and communities by offering a citizen-centric prosumption services driven disruptive technologies, SDG 12 responsible consumption and production from RES to support the sharing, trading and use of clean energy, and SDG 13 climate action toward decarbonization thereby lessening CO₂ emissions from fossil based energy sources.

5.2. Research implications

The energy sector is experiencing rapid change due to disruption from digitization, decentralization, and decarbonization. The use of disruptive technologies such as AI, DLT, and IoT can help to manage their green shift. For example, AI can help with optimization of the power grid to successfully maintain reliability and resilience [1]. IoT through the use of on-board sensing and communication protocols can contribute to support data analytics and remote monitoring of off-grid energy systems. The data produced from IoT devices such as energy metering devices can be use by AI for predictive and responsive maintenance. DLT promotes transparent by offering the audit trails for energy. Also, smart contracts can be deployed to automate energy trading transactions via a publicly verifiable manner [43].

Thus, DLT can enable the transitioning to decentralized peer-to-peer

energy sharing and trading ecosystem for energy prosumers aided by AI that can adjust the energy consumers demand according to the available RES generation while supplying the local non-grid owned flexible loads [4]. This study promotes the convergence of emerging technologies to improve the intelligence, automation, communication, and distribution towards a digitalized energy internet to decentralized and accelerate a flexible energy sharing and trading network within actualization of DEPC. This study adds to the work of [16], highlighting that the increasing demand for electricity as well as the emergence of RES, and the digitalization of energy systems. Theoretically this article provides a multidisciplinary approach that support the design of an intelligent energy trading platforms.

5.3. Implication for policy

In distributed energy prosumer communities, there is an increasing need for flexibility from RES which could be used for arbitrage in the electricity markets or for congestion management for example in balancing the power grid [55]. However, most electricity markets employ a centralized market-based mechanisms for trading energy resources. For optimal energy trading smaller localized markets or energy prosumers could also fill a niche for enabling the consumption of RES by participating in the electricity markets by sharing electricity and also aiding in the management of the entire local distribution network. Accordingly, this article develops an energy system architecture as a decentralized approach for managing energy flexibility towards balancing energy demand and energy generation in distributed energy prosumer communities.

The developed architecture creates a blueprint for deploying a fully decentralized peer-to-peer energy sharing and trading mechanism, which may not include any intermediary third party. The developed energy system architecture can be employed as a best practice for energy policy practitioners to generate more transparent, robust, replicable, and policy-relevant approach in future DEPC. As stated in the literature [4], the energy system architecture can support existing or new energy flexibility market allowing energy prosumers to trade their flexibility via a peer-to-peer fashion digitally using smart contracts that employs tokens which allows for the measurement of prosumers-owned flexibility.

5.4. Practical implications

It is envisioned that in future neighborhoods energy consumers will be energy prosumers thus not only consuming energy but also producing and storing energy through a decentralized manner. The emergent of disruptive technologies such as AI, DLT, and IoT possess the capability to transform and improve neighborhoods and districts into distributed energy prosumer communities. For example, AI can predict energy consumption of energy consumers by analyzing and processing energy related data collected from IoT based energy metering devices. These predictions can be utilized for decision making support and also provide monetary gain to energy consumers towards demand-side management [35]. Therefore, this study proposed the use of DLT and smart contracts to enable energy transactions based on a peer-to-peer approach.

DLT analyzes energy production and consumption using smart contracts which allows energy prosumers (energy consumer producing energy from their own installed RES such as Solar PV panels mounted at rooftop) to track energy production and trading of energy transaction in a distributed manner. Furthermore, AI is suggested to assist energy consumers in forecasting the dynamic price change for electricity consumption for each hour facilitating demand response management for household appliances in specifying time when the electricity price is lowest. Moreover, AI based ML provides energy optimization towards adjusting users' usage pattern for behavioral change and offers recommendations on the electricity usage patterns to the user thereby helping to reduce their electricity bills [35]. In the energy sector AI also offers several other value-added services such as demand forecasting, data

virtualization, energy storage facilitation, energy resource management, prediction, and prevention of energy system failure.

6. Conclusion

This current study aims to examine the technological convergence artificial intelligence with distributed ledger technologies and Internet of Things to decentralized and accelerate distributed energy prosumer communities. To this end, a proof-of-concept based energy system architecture model was developed which can support energy consumers and energy prosumers to bilaterally share and trade energy within their local community via the microgrid. The energy system architecture goes beyond the state-of-the-art by employing smart contracts to enable secure energy transactions and real-time transaction settlement and validation. Also, ensuring that the electricity networks is robust and without completely relying on a centralized supervision and control of energy demand and supply. The developed energy system architecture can contribute to the ongoing research around energy communities by enabling energy prosumers to monetize surplus energy and record its provenance by supporting their flexibility integration into the electricity market.

Key findings from this study explored how DLT can enable the storing of energy related data and also enable energy transactions in a secured and tamper proof manner and how AI and IoT can support the development of a distributed energy prosumer communities. Also, the finding discusses how DLT, smart contracts, and AI can enable a decentralized peer-to-peer local energy sharing and trading in distributed energy prosumer communities. Findings from this study presents a use case on use of the energy system architecture (levering DLT and AI), to improve microgrid operations. As future work, it is intended that a tool will be implemented that leverages the capabilities of AI, DLT and smart contracts to autonomously support a decentralized and distributed energy prosumer communities. Moreover, there is need to investigate the applicability of the developed energy system architecture for supporting the deployment of a local self-sustainable distributed energy prosumer communities in Norway. Additionally, the developed energy system architecture can be extended to support the management of cross-commodity or utilities besides from electricity such as water, gas, heat, and energy related services such as electric mobility, etc.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Bokolo Anthony Jnr: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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